

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		30-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		Skolasky et al.	
Country of origin		USA	
Publication year		2018	
Title of article		Telephone-Based Intervention to Improve Rehabilitation Engagement After Spinal Stenosis Surgery: A Prospective Lagged Controlled Trial	
Title of journal		Journal of Bone & Joint Surgery, American	
Volume 2018;100	Issue 1	Pages 21-30 (epub 1-20)	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify): A Prospective Lagged Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, p. 1, 8
Participants	Patients undergoing lumbar spinal stenosis surgical procedure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Title, p. 1, 3, 4, 7
Types of intervention	Health behavior change counseling	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1-8
Types of comparison	Usual care	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1-8
Types of outcome measures	Pain, function disability/status, quality of life, activity	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 4-5

INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>
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Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	To compare the effectiveness of health behavior change counseling with usual care for improving health outcomes after a lumbar spinal stenosis surgical procedure.	Abstract, p. 2-3
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	A lagged controlled trial	Title, p. 1, 8
Start date	December 2009	p. 3
End date	August 2012	p. 3
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Unclear Not reported. This study was approved by our institutional review board.	p. 3

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	An academic spine center at a community-based hospital	p. 3
Inclusion criteria	Patients with lumbar spondylolisthesis or scoliosis also underwent arthrodesis. Patients were ≥ 18 years of age, were English-speaking, and were able to provide informed consent.	p. 3
Exclusion criteria	Patients who had undergone a previous lumbar spine surgical procedure were excluded.	p. 3
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear All participants provided written informed consent.	p. 3

Intervention group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Health behavior change counseling	p. 4

No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=63 (M:25, F:38) Mean age = 60	p. 18 (table 1) p. 18 (table 1)
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	All elements of usual care. Three similarly timed telephone calls. During the preoperative call, the study therapist used motivational interviewing strategies to increase the patient's perception of the importance of physical therapy to recovery and confidence to follow through with rehabilitation. The therapist identified barriers to engagement and facilitated commitment to behavior change.	p. 4

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Usual care	p. 4, 5, 18 (table 1)
No. randomised to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=59 (M:20, F:39) Mean age = 58	p. 18 (table 1) p. 18 (table 1)
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Usual care involved routine clinical management of signs and symptoms of lumbar spinal stenosis. This consisted of preoperative evaluation with physical examination and imaging, decompression surgery with or without arthrodesis, postoperative rehabilitation with clinic-based and home-based physical therapy, and postoperative assessment with physical examination and imaging. All participants in the usual care group received 3 scheduled telephone calls to account for the attention received by the health behavior change counseling group. During these calls, the study therapist asked participants about their progress. Medical questions were directed to the treating surgeon.	p. 4

Outcomes

Outcome 1 Postoperative Assessment

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain	p. 5
Outcome definition (with diagnostic criteria if relevant)	Brief Pain Inventory (BPI) Favors intervention	p. 5

Outcome 2 Postoperative Assessment

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Disability	p. 5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Oswestry Disability Index (ODI) Favors intervention	p. 5

Outcome 3 Postoperative Assessment

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Health status	p. 5
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Medical Outcomes Study 12-item Short-Form Health Survey, version 2 (SF-12) Favors intervention	p. 5

Outcome 4 Preoperative Assessment

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Activity	p. 4
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Patient activation Measure	p. 4

Follow up

Follow up	3 years (36 months)	p. 3
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Conclusion	<p>Results: By 12 months, health behavior change counseling participants reported significantly greater reductions in pain intensity ($p = 0.008$) and disability ($p = 0.028$) and significantly greater improvement in physical health compared with usual care participants ($p = 0.025$). These differences were attenuated by 24 and 36 months after the surgical procedure. Early improvements in health outcomes were mediated by improvements in physical therapist-rated engagement and self-reported attendance at physical therapy sessions in the health behavior change counseling group.</p> <p>Conclusions: Health behavior change counseling improved health outcomes during the first 12 months after the surgical procedure through changes in rehabilitation engagement. Wider use of health behavior change counseling may lead to improved outcomes not only after lumbar spine surgery but also in other conditions for which rehabilitation is key to recovery.</p>	<p>Abstract</p> <p>p. 128</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>